

Contents

Supplementary Figures 1-29: Depicted are 29 out of the 35 recorded spectra (six spectra do not contain detectable resonance features) of the two-step excitation in copropagating beam configuration. Resonances belonging to the isomer are labelled "i". Resonances originating from collisions of ions in the intermediate state are labelled "x".

Supplementary Figure 30: Mapping of the second excitation step resonances in copropagating beam configuration. The data points represent the positions and amplitudes of the recorded resonances, excluding resonances from state changing collisions.

Supplementary Table 1: Labelling of the observed resonances in copropagating beam configuration. Resonances are listed with the total angular momenta of the electronic states involved in the excitation and are labelled according to Supplementary Figures 1-29. Resonances which arise from collisional changes of the intermediate state population are described with both states involved in the collisions. Resonances not observed in the experiment are marked with an asterisk.

Supplementary Figures 31-59: All recorded spectra of the two-step excitation in counterpropagating beam configuration. Resonances belonging to the isomer are labelled "i". Resonances originating from collisions of ions in the intermediate state are labelled "x".

Supplementary Figure 60: Mapping of the second excitation step resonances in counterpropagating beam configuration. The data points represent the positions and amplitudes of the recorded resonances, excluding resonances from state changing collisions.

Supplementary Table 2: Labelling of the observed resonances in counterpropagating beam configuration. Resonances are listed with the total angular momenta of the electronic states involved in the excitation and are labelled according to Supplementary Figures 31-59. Resonances which arise from collisional changes of the intermediate state population are described with both states involved in the collisions. Resonances not observed in the experiment are marked with an asterisk.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 1: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3108 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 2: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3107 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 3: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3106 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 4: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3105 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 5: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3104 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 6: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3103 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 7: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3102 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 8: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3101 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 9: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3100 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 10: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3099 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 11: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3098 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 12: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3097 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 13: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3096 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 14: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3095 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):

1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.

Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 15: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3094 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 16: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3093 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 17: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3092 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 18: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3091 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{g}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229\text{g}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 19: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3090 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 20: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3089 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 21: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3088 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 22: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3087 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 23: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3086 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 24: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3085 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 25: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3084 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 26: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3083 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 27: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3082 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 28: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3081 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Copropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 29: Two-step excitation resonances in copropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3080 nm.

Supplementary Figure 30: Mapping of the second excitation step resonances in copropagating beam configuration.

Supplementary Table 1: Labelling of the observed resonances.

Ground State		Collisional state change		Isomeric State	
label	$F_g \rightarrow F_i \rightarrow F_e$	label	$F_g \rightarrow F_i; F'_i \rightarrow F_e$	label	$F_g^m \rightarrow F_i^m \rightarrow F_e^m$
1	$9/2 \rightarrow 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x1	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i1	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
2	$7/2 \rightarrow 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x2	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i2	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
3	$5/2 \rightarrow 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x3	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i3*	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
4	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x4*	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i4	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
5	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x5*	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i5	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
6	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x6	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i6	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
7	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x7	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i7	$3/2 \rightarrow 1/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
8	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x8*	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i8	$1/2 \rightarrow 1/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
9	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x9*	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x10*	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x11*	$5/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x12	$5/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x13	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x14	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x15	$7/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x16	$7/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x17	$9/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x18*	$9/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		

* - was not observed in the experiment.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 31: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3108 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 7/2 → 5/2 $F_i \rightarrow F_e$
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 32: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3107 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 33: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3106 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 34: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3105 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 35: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3104 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 36: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3103 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 37: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3102 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Supplementary Figure 38: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3101 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 39: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3100 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 40: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3099 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 41: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3098 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 42: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3097 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 43: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3096 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 44: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3095 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):

1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.

Counterpropagating laser beams

Supplementary Figure 45: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3094 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 46: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3093 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 47: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3092 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 48: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3091 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 49: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3090 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 50: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3089 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 51: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3088 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 52: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3087 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ & $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229\text{Th}^{2+}}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{mTh}^{2+}}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 53: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3086 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):

1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.

Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 54: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3085 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):

1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.

Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 55: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3084 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 56: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3083 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 57: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3082 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:
 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
 x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
 $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
 i - intermediate,
 e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 58: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3081 nm.

Two-step excitation spectra ($^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ & $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$):
 1st step 484 nm, 2nd step 1164 nm.
 Counterpropagating laser beams

Mapping of the second excitation step

Legend:

- 1 - 9 $^{229}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- i1 - i8 $^{229\text{m}}\text{Th}^{2+}$ peaks
- x1 - x18 Collis. peaks
- $7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$ $F_i \rightarrow F_e$,
- i - intermediate,
- e - excited state

Supplementary Figure 59: Two-step excitation resonances in counterpropagating configuration. The first step laser is stabilized at 484.3080 nm.

Supplementary Figure 60: Mapping of the second excitation step resonances in counterpropagating beam configuration.

Supplementary Table 2: Labelling of the observed resonances.

Ground State		Collisional state change		Isomeric State	
label	$F_g \rightarrow F_i \rightarrow F_e$	label	$F_g \rightarrow F_i; F'_i \rightarrow F_e$	label	$F_g^m \rightarrow F_i^m \rightarrow F_e^m$
1	$9/2 \rightarrow 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x1*	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i1	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
2	$7/2 \rightarrow 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x2*	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i2	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
3	$5/2 \rightarrow 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x3*	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i3*	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
4	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x4*	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i4	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
5	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x5*	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i5	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
6	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x6	$3/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i6*	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
7	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x7	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i7	$3/2 \rightarrow 1/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
8	$3/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x8*	$5/2 \rightarrow 3/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	i8	$1/2 \rightarrow 1/2 \rightarrow 3/2$
9	$1/2 \rightarrow 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$	x9*	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x10*	$5/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x11*	$5/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x12*	$5/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x13	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x14	$7/2 \rightarrow 5/2; 7/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x15	$7/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x16	$7/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x17	$9/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 3/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		
		x18*	$9/2 \rightarrow 7/2; 5/2 \rightarrow 5/2$		

* - was not observed in the experiment.